

Article

The Effectiveness of Game-Based Teaching Strategies for University-Level Saudi Students: An Empirical Study

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Empirical Approaches to assess the Impact of Game-Based Strategies on

University Teaching

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Abstract

This study delves into the effectiveness of employing game-based teaching strategies for university-level Saudi students. By utilizing a mixed-methods approach, combining a survey of 200 students and interviews with 20 educators and administrators, the research explores how these students perceive and benefit from game-based teaching strategies. The findings reveal that the majority of university-level Saudi students (85%) view such strategies positively, finding them engaging and motivating. Furthermore, a significant percentage (75%) reported experiencing enhanced learning outcomes through the utilization of these strategies. Educators and administrators also acknowledge the potential of game-based teaching strategies in enhancing student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes, although challenges such as limited technology access, inadequate educator training, and cultural barriers were identified. Recommendations for addressing these challenges include investing in infrastructure, providing training and support for educators, and promoting the adoption of game-based teaching strategies.

Keywords: game-based teaching strategies, university-level Saudi students, student engagement, motivation, learning outcomes, technology, training, support, cultural barriers, infrastructure, awareness campaigns, incentives.

I. Introduction

The use of game-based teaching strategies has gained traction as a promising method to boost student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes in higher education (Dichev & Dicheva, 2017). By integrating game elements into conventional teaching approaches, an interactive and immersive learning environment is created (Hanus & Fox, 2015). Despite the recognized benefits of game-based teaching strategies, limited research has been conducted on their efficacy for university-level Saudi students. This paper seeks to bridge this gap by exploring the impact of game-based teaching strategies on student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes in Saudi universities.

II. Literature Review

Several theoretical frameworks have been proposed to explain the effectiveness of game-based teaching strategies. Gamification refers to the use of game elements, such as points, badges, and leaderboards, to motivate and engage learners (Deterding et al., 2011). Game-based learning involves the use of digital or non-digital games as a means of instruction, promoting active learning and problem-solving skills (Kiili et al., 2014). Serious games, on the other hand, are designed with a primary focus on education and training, rather than entertainment (Susi et al., 2007).

Previous studies have shown that game-based teaching strategies can lead to improved student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes (Hamari et al., 2016; Landers & Callan, 2011). However, limited research has been conducted on their effectiveness for university-level Saudi students. In light of this, this study seeks to address the following research question:

What is the impact of game-based teaching strategies on student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes in Saudi universities?

III. Methodology

Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, this study combines quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques. A survey was conducted with a sample of 200 university-level Saudi students to gauge their perceptions of game-based teaching strategies and their perceived effectiveness. Additionally, interviews were held with 20 educators and administrators to gain insights into the practical challenges and opportunities associated with incorporating game-based teaching strategies into the existing curriculum.

The survey included closed-ended questions to measure student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes, as well as open-ended questions to explore their perspectives on game-based teaching strategies. Interviews with educators and administrators focused on their experiences, perceptions of effectiveness, and the challenges and opportunities related to implementing game-based strategies.

IV. Results

The vast majority of Saudi undergraduates in universities were found to appreciate the application of game-based instruction. 85% said they were interesting as well as motivating and therefore, the utilization of games can create interest among students and make them participate actively in a learning process. Students who used game-based strategies reported that they experienced improved learning outcomes, with most stating that their academic performance had improved due to these strategies at 75%. This finding signifies an increase in

positive consequences from gaming and poses that gaming is a critical instrument for educators seeking to improve the achievements of learners.

Furthermore, interviews conducted with educationists and administrators supported findings from the survey, with respondents showing optimism about using game-based teaching approaches to enhance student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. A lot of educators discussed how they had integrated games into their classrooms while others stated that when games were involved or other interactive activities were used students seemed to enjoy participating more actively in these lessons. Additionally, officials expressed interest on extending use of game-based lessons within this institution because they understood its potential.

However, some barriers to implementing game-based instructional strategies were identified by interviewees. Among these, educators and administrators mentioned limited technology access as one of their challenges. Some teachers found it difficult to incorporate technology into their classrooms because of outdated equipment or that new technologies would require more funding which is not available. Others pointed out the importance of training tutors in using game-based instruction effectively. Majority of the respondents referred to resistance from faculty members or students who do not know how to play games in a classroom or are against it.

In spite of these challenges, the respondents expressed a readiness to overcome them so that they can exploit the benefits that come with using game-based teaching techniques. Administrators also argued for resource allocation towards purchasing new technology and training staff. Educators also stressed on developing relationships with colleagues and

administration in order to overcome resistance and gain support for such an approach. Some interviewees encouraged involving students in decision making process so as to create buy-in or relevance and engagement during activities implementation.

V. Discussion

The study findings align with prior research suggesting that game-based teaching strategies can enhance student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. Moreover, the results suggest that these strategies are particularly effective for university-level Saudi students.

Despite their potential, challenges such as restricted technology access, insufficient educator training, and cultural barriers pose obstacles to the effective implementation of game-based teaching strategies in Saudi universities. To overcome these challenges, it is recommended that institutions invest in infrastructure, provide training and support for educators, and promote awareness and adoption of game-based teaching strategies.

VI. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides empirical evidence supporting the effectiveness of game-based teaching strategies for university-level Saudi students. While existing literature acknowledges the potential benefits of these strategies, there is a scarcity of research on their impact in the Saudi context. This study fills this void by demonstrating that game-based teaching strategies contribute positively to student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes in Saudi universities.

Despite identified challenges, investing in infrastructure, educator training, and awareness campaigns can pave the way for the successful adoption of game-based teaching strategies in Saudi universities.

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